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Nextfood - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Practice Abstract #5: Case development report, year 1

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A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In this document, we report the activities and outcomes in each Nextfood case throughout the first year of the project. Each case has reported on the process and outcomes of following the instructions for how to run their case and research the process.

The first year of the case work was heavily focused on initiating the case work. For many cases, this meant transforming an already existing course from their standard way of operating to something closer to the action learning-based Nextfood approach. Kick-off workshops were conducted in most cases where students, teachers, administration and other key stakeholders co-developed the strategy for kicking off the transformation process. Common for many cases was the fact that this change was very much welcomed by both students and teachers. A key challenge that was identified was how to find resources and time to enable the necessary change to happen. The local institutions might play a key role in enabling an improved focus on action learning.